

FIGURE ANALYSIS WHEN DESIGNING PATTERNS

Tukhtaeva Zebo Sharifovna

Dean of the faculty of textile and leather industry, doctor of pedagogical sciences,
professor of the Bukhara Engineering and Technology Institute

E-mail: zebo-7171@mail.ru

Azimova Firusa Kamolovna

Coister-steager of the Department of Innovative Technologies of the Light Industry
"of the Bukhara Engineering Technological Institute

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье рассмотрены вопросы анализа фигуры, данные учитывающие при построении выкройки, моделировании одежды, способы построения основы выкройки, обмере роста при определении размера одежды, пропорции и пропорциональности фигуры.

Ключевые слова: метод, построение основы, выкройка, лекало, модел, фигура, одежда, пропорция, пропорциональность, рост, размер.

ABSTRACT

In this article, the analysis of the figure is considered questions, and what to consider when constructing patterns, modeling clothes, a method for building the base of the pattern, measuring growth in determining the size of clothing, proportion and proportionality of the figure.

Keywords: method, constructing the base, patterns, pattern, modeling, clothing, proportion, proportionality, height and size.

INTRODUCTION

Any method of building the foundation is designed for a more or less proportional figure, close to the typical one. Not many women can boast of an ideal body structure. The basic pattern can be checked and adjusted to fit the figure even before the fabric sample is made. The initial stages of design are associated with the appearance of tailored clothing. To cut (French tailler) - literally translated means to make according to height, according to the measure. Clothing design is the development of a design (construction, relative position and configuration of parts) of a clothing model. It consists of the following stages - the choice of methodology, the development of product drawings for a preliminary design, calculation, construction of

a drawing (using individual or standard measurements), making patterns, drawing up working documentation.

METHODS

Clothing, which originally arose mainly to protect the human body from adverse climatic conditions, atmospheric influences, under the influence of various historical, social and economic conditions, national characteristics, society has undergone many changes, has reached a great variety of types and forms of applied art.

As a result of the construction by individual standards, approximately such a pattern is obtained - the base (front and back), but it can also differ significantly, this is normal, everyone's figures are different, so the designs are also different. But, if the type of pattern is completely abnormal, it is necessary to check everything and correct it in accordance with the features of the figure.

Under the design of clothing is meant the calculation and drawing of the structure, the development of calculations and constructive modeling. One of the main tasks of designing clothes is to obtain shells of bodies of a spatial form from a flat material and solve the inverse problem, i.e. bending (straightening) parts of the surface of clothing onto a plane, - building sweeps of clothing details.

The purpose of designing clothes is: to learn how to correctly produce drawings for any human figure.

Clothing modeling is a change in the design lines of the basic product drawing for a new model of any complexity. Structural lines are contour lines of details (mainly seams) that divide the surface of clothing into separate parts (details), creating its three-dimensional shape and characterizing its appearance.

The history of improving the form and design of clothing can be divided into two directions: the first is evolutionary growth along with the development of the individual and society, and the second is the development of the form and design of clothing under the influence of fashion. In the process of clothing development, experience is accumulated, cuts are typified, certain elements of its design are fixed, and clothing is modified in accordance with changing living conditions: the material and technical base and general culture.

Clothing design is the preparation of drawings of details for tailoring the finished product.

Currently, there are many different methods of designing clothes. All existing clothing design methods can be divided into:

- approximate methods for obtaining basic clothing designs;
- engineering methods.

Approximate Methods:

- calculation and graphic methods;
- dummy method (dummy method).

The main task of clothing design is the development of drawings of details for an individual or typical figure. Each design technique includes information about the figure of a person or a finished product, methods for processing the information received in the form of technical calculations and formulas that set the dimensions of constructive segments and assemblies of clothing parts, and methods for geometric construction and division of the clothing structure. When designing, the features of the physique, cut and methods of technological processing are taken into account, that is, what ultimately forms a permanent system of internal information inherent in each technique.

RESULTS

When developing a design, one should proceed not only from the requirements for clothing as an item of personal consumption, but at the same time take into account the requirements as an object of mass production. From these positions, the design should:

- match the original model in terms of silhouette, shape, construction lines, finishes, etc. This is achieved due to the accuracy of the calculation of patterns;
- contribute to the formation of a set of properties, taking into account the requirements for clothing. This is, first of all, the conformity of the design to the size and shape of the human body, ease of use, providing comfortable conditions for the functioning of the body, high wear resistance, etc.;
- be economical and technological at the same time. This is especially important for the conditions of mass production of garments. Economical is the design, the creation of which is characterized by the lowest both costs and waste materials. Manufacturability is associated with minimization of labor costs for the manufacture of the product;
- ensure a good fit of the product on the human figure. It is laid down in the design drawings and to a certain extent depends on the correctness of the calculations. At the same time, it is necessary to take into account the influence of possible loads on individual components, parts in the process of future operation of products, leading to a change in their shape [2].

When using ready-made patterns from fashion magazines, you definitely need to pay attention to this dimension. The magazines always indicate how tall the pattern is made.

It is more reliable to build the basis of the figure and use it to model the product. When using ready-made patterns from fashion magazines, you definitely need to pay

attention to this dimension. The magazines always indicate how tall the pattern is made. If the height is different, such a pattern can be used, but it is necessary to adjust the length (not only to reduce or increase the length of the product, but also to change the length to the waist, the length to the armhole, the height of the chest, the location of the pockets).(Figure 1)

Figure 1. Modeling of a robe with a front closure

Naturally, the optimal choice of the structural scheme of the product is necessary, the division of its individual elements, which would provide the most acceptable conditions for the "work" of materials and parts in all areas of clothing;

- provide the ability to create a family of structures based on the optimal one (method of basic structures).

The height of the shoulders is determined by the vertical distance from the tangent to the seventh cervical vertebra to the lowest point of the shoulder slope. There are normal, low-shouldered and high-shouldered figures.

Since the shape and dimensions of the body change with age, this should be taken into account when developing a dimensional typology and in design.

Conventionally, the population is divided into three groups: younger (20-29 years old), middle (30-44 years old) and older (45 years old and older). This division is due to the completion of the formation of the human body by the age of 20 and significant changes in the physique after 60 years.

DISCUSSION

Growth is a very important dimension: it is taken into account when determining the size of clothes, and when calculating patterns determines some proportions. Therefore, with an inaccurate measurement of growth, the pattern may be constructed incorrectly.

The proportions of a figure are the ratio of the magnitudes of various parts of the human body [3]. Knowing the features of the proportions of the figure, it is easier to choose the shape and style of clothing that hides the shortcomings of the body structure (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Modeling women's evening dress

The proportionality of the figure can be determined visually or with the help of a photograph. You can take a full-length photo (you need to stand straight), measure the proportions with a ruler, checking with the scheme of standard proportions, taking the size of the head as the measurement module.

It is necessary to pay attention to the ratio of height to length up to the waist, to length up to the hips. There are such figures in which the center of the body is slightly shifted up or down. It is also advisable to check the ratio of the width of the shoulders and pelvis, usually the width of the shoulders of some is slightly less than the width of the pelvis.

In case of deviation of proportions from the norm, it is necessary to choose the right shape and style of clothing, listening to the advice of specialists in order to create a certain visual effect with its help. Since the proportions of the body are closely related to the physique [4].

Structural additions are finally specified in the process of manufacturing a model sample. The development of a model design is reduced to the introduction of model features into the developed drawing of the basic basis of the structure. To do this, the tucks are moved on the shelf and back, the construction of coquettes, reliefs, etc.

CONCLUSION

The process of creating any new thing can be represented as the following scheme: demand-planning-forecasting-designing-production-replication-distribution-consumption. The starting point of the designer's creativity is the needs of man and society as a whole. The basis of any design is taking into account the comprehensive needs of a potential consumer. It is this study of needs that is the main content of the pre-project analysis when creating a new thing [5].

Pre-project analysis - a study carried out at the initial stage of design and comparison of data on the desired functions of a thing, on the appearance of the

designed product, on the method of manufacture, on the presence of analogues of the proposed object. Such an analysis helps to identify the shortcomings of existing products, as well as the wishes of consumers.

In addition to pre-design analysis, when designing a new product, they resort to socio-economic analysis, functional analysis, functional cost analysis, form analysis and technological analysis.

Therefore, we can conclude that the analysis of the human figure in the construction of the design of clothing depends on a number of indicators and measurements that serve to build the design and pattern of clothing.

REFERENCES

1. Bakhtiorovna, T.B. *Technical innovative-educational environment*.
2. Negmatovna, N.G., & Erkinovna, U.V. *Meaning Of Spiritual Heritage Of Khodja Ali Romitaniy. International Journal of Early Childhood*, 14(03), 2022.
3. Sharifovna, T.Z., & Bakhriniso, T. *Modernization of higher education by solving integration problems*.
4. Sharifovna, T.Z., Khamidovna, S.K., Bakhtiyorovna, T.B., & Fakhritdinovna, M.S. (2020). *Improving Higher Education Through Integrated Learning, Features Of An Integrated Lesson. European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine*, 7(03), 2020.
5. Akhmedzhanova, F.A. *Ways to improve the quality of snacks // Molodoy ucheniy. — 2019. — № 24 (262). — C. 531-533.*
6. http://lecalo.kuznk.ru/view_dress_basis_post.php?id=2